

Tracking Urban Order in Micromobility

A Spatial Order Index for Monitoring Geofenced Parking Interventions*

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Abstract

This paper proposes an entropy-based Spatial Order Index for monitoring changes associated with geofenced parking interventions in shared micromobility systems. Implemented as virtual parking zones or designated parking locations, such interventions are intended to reduce disorderly parking and structure vehicle distribution in urban space. The paper develops an objective measure of spatial order by deriving the index from summarizable count-based primitives and Shannon entropy in a form suitable for systematic reporting. The present version applies the approach to operational micromobility data from Düsseldorf, where spatial order is analyzed over time across parking-prohibition zones and related to the rollout of geofenced designated parking locations. Across the study period, the monthly index rises from 0.225 in January 2023 to 0.367 in early 2026 and shows a strong positive association with the number of designated parking locations ($r = 0.969$). These results illustrate how the index can be used to monitor changes in parking patterns associated with urban parking regulation. Because the method is based on a standardized count-based representation, it is also suitable for comparative analyses across different urban areas and, in principle, across different cities.

Version note. This first preprint version focuses on the methodological development of the Spatial Order Index and its initial empirical application to Düsseldorf. Additional case studies are intended to extend the empirical scope in subsequent versions.

1 Introduction

Shared micromobility has evolved from early station-based bicycle rental systems to digitally managed free-floating services for bicycles and e-scooters. Early large-scale systems such as Vélib' demonstrated the urban potential of shared mobility, but they were constrained by fixed docking infrastructure and corresponding limits in operational flexibility. Later developments in GPS tracking, mobile applications, and connected vehicle technology enabled more flexible dockless systems, allowing users to locate, unlock, and park vehicles directly via smartphone. This broader development has expanded the reach of shared mobility and strengthened its integration into multimodal urban transport systems [1].

At the same time, the operational flexibility of free-floating systems has created growing challenges for the management of public space, as shared vehicles are often parked on pavements or in other unsuitable locations, thereby reducing accessibility and creating conflicts with pedestrians and other road users. In North Rhine-Westphalia, case law has clarified that the station-independent commercial placement of shared vehicles in public street space may constitute *Sondernutzung*; this was first established for rental bicycles in the *Call a Bike* case and later applied expressly to free-floating e-scooters.[2, 3] The practical relevance of this issue became particularly visible in Düsseldorf, where the combined fleet of

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the five e-scooter operators reached 12,700 vehicles in August 2021, shortly before the city tightened its regulatory framework through a new *Sondernutzungssatzung*. [4, 5]

Düsseldorf provides a particularly relevant case for studying these effects. In May 2022, the city opened its first mobility hub at Stadttor, integrating bicycles, e-scooters, and car-sharing services. By March 2026, this network had grown to 30 mobility hubs, with further expansion planned. In parallel, the city established a dense network of digitally defined designated parking locations for e-scooters and bikes. As of March 2026, Düsseldorf had implemented 268 such designated parking locations across the city, with a network that extends beyond the city centre and continues to expand. For e-scooters in particular, these virtually marked zones are intended to reduce sidewalk clutter and improve public order by steering parking behaviour toward designated locations.

This creates a practical and methodological question: how can changes associated with such geofenced parking interventions be measured in a way that is operationally useful, comparable over time, and suitable for systematic reporting? Recent literature has addressed shared micromobility from several adjacent perspectives, including general system impacts and regulation [6, 7], the planning and implementation of geofenced or designated parking infrastructure [8, 9], and the role of geofencing and city dashboards in data-driven micromobility governance [10]. A related operational perspective is provided by recent work on geofenced bike-sharing parking that proposes local parking-load indicators, but this still differs from the present focus on an index for measuring changes in spatial order over time [11]. In addition, the entropy concept used here is, of course, not new; it originates in Shannon’s foundational work on information theory, in which the logarithmic form follows from an additivity requirement for independent choices [12]. However, existing micromobility studies appear to focus primarily on infrastructure design, operational practice, or local parking-performance measures rather than on an index for measuring changes in spatial order over time that is derived from summarizable count-based data.

The starting point of the paper is therefore the practical need for an order index that is not only conceptually meaningful, but also operationally usable in recurring BI-style reporting. Such an index must remain interpretable under aggregation and therefore be derived from summarizable base measures rather than from averages of already computed index values.

The present paper therefore contributes not a new entropy concept as such, but its adaptation into an entropy-based Spatial Order Index for micromobility parking patterns. Because Shannon entropy can be expressed as a deterministic function of additive count-based primitives, it provides a theoretically grounded basis for exactly this requirement. The argument of the paper follows this logic explicitly: it first derives the BI requirements implied by the need for an order index, then shows why Shannon entropy is suitable because of its count-based decomposition, formalizes the resulting Spatial Order Index, and finally evaluates the approach empirically for Düsseldorf. In this sense, the contribution is twofold. First, the index is derived from summarizable, additive base measures in a way that is consistent with business intelligence (BI) reporting principles. Second, the paper applies the index to the case of Düsseldorf in order to examine whether the rollout of designated parking locations is associated with a measurable increase in spatial order.

2 Data Foundation

This study is based on data from shared mobility providers, made available through the Mobility Data Specification (MDS), an open standard maintained by the Open Mobility Foundation for data exchange between public authorities and shared mobility providers [13]. Access to these data, as well as their processing and publication for analytical purposes, was governed by data-sharing agreements and the applicable legal and contractual conditions.

The primary automated source is the MDS Provider API, in particular the `/vehicles` endpoint, which provides standardized real-time information on vehicle status, availability, and location [13]. In Düsseldorf,

these real-time data are collected hourly from the city’s shared mobility providers. The resulting sequence of snapshots forms a spatio-temporal dataset that makes it possible to reconstruct historical operational patterns and vehicle distributions over time.

To ingest and process these data, automated ELT workflows transfer the MDS snapshots into a spatially enabled relational database, where transformation and loading are performed primarily within the database engine.

In addition to the MDS snapshots, the analysis draws on manually curated operational geodata maintained in the database. These reference data include, for example, the geometries of designated parking locations and related temporal attributes such as the start and end dates of their validity. They provide the spatial and regulatory context required to relate observed vehicle locations to station-based interventions.

Together, these data sources provide a structured spatio-temporal basis for analysing deployment patterns, spatial distribution, station usage, and compliance-related conditions. More broadly, recent micromobility research has highlighted the analytical value of passively generated mobility data while also emphasizing the importance of preprocessing, data quality assessment, and potential bias mitigation [14, 15].

3 Choosing an Appropriate Spatial Resolution

The choice of spatial resolution is a key methodological decision, as it determines the level at which spatial order is represented and measured. In the present context, this choice is governed by the interaction of three distinct spatial scales. First, the resolution must be coarse enough to absorb typical GPS uncertainty and short-range positional scatter. Second, it must remain fine enough to distinguish nearby designated parking locations or other local attractors intended to structure parking behaviour. Third, if the indicator is to be used in dashboard-based reporting and possible future cross-city comparisons, the grid should be embedded in a harmonized reference framework rather than being defined only in an arbitrary local metric projection.

The first of these scales arises from the properties of the positioning data itself. Shared e-scooters and bikes are typically equipped with consumer-grade GNSS receivers rather than professional geodetic systems. Under favourable open-sky conditions, well-designed GPS receivers can achieve horizontal accuracies of about 3 m and vertical accuracies of about 5 m, each with 95% probability [16]. However, official GPS guidance also notes that accuracy deteriorates in the presence of buildings, bridges, trees, and other sources of signal blockage and reflection [17]. In dense urban environments, this degradation can be much stronger. Recent work on smartphone GNSS in urban canyons shows that urban observations are heavily affected by multipath and non-line-of-sight effects, which can substantially increase positional uncertainty and generate structured spatial scatter rather than purely random noise [18]. From the GPS perspective alone, a plausible spatial-resolution range therefore lies roughly between 5 m and 30 m: the lower bound is suggested by typical open-sky accuracy, while the upper bound reflects the scale of typical urban multipath effects.

To complement these general considerations with evidence from the operational data, positional scatter was also examined directly in the MDS vehicle records. For this purpose, observations of apparently stationary scooters were identified from temporally consecutive location records, and for each observation the distance to the mean position of its local cluster was calculated. The resulting radius distribution provides an empirical measure of small-scale positional variation in the data. As shown in [figure 1](#), most observations are concentrated within a few metres of their local centre, while the upper tail extends into the low tens of metres. This empirical pattern is broadly consistent with the ranges suggested by the cited GNSS literature and supports the conclusion that resolutions far below the 10 m scale would be difficult to justify.

Figure 1: Distribution of distances between individual scooter observations and the mean position of their local stationary cluster. The vertical lines mark the median and the 95% quantile of the observed radius distribution.

The second scale is determined by the urban parking structure that the analysis aims to resolve. If the spatial resolution is too coarse, nearby sharing stations or other distinct parking attractors may collapse into the same spatial unit and can no longer be distinguished analytically. In that case, the resulting representation would underestimate the extent to which parking behaviour aligns with specific designated locations. This consideration is inherently local, as it depends on the spacing of nearby designated parking locations and on the density of relevant urban attractors in the study area. In the Düsseldorf data, the minimum nearest-neighbour distance between designated parking locations is 15.8 m, the 5% quantile is 34.1 m, the 25% quantile is 97.1 m, and the median is 130.3 m. This indicates that very closely spaced locations do occur, but are exceptional. A spatial resolution of 25 m therefore remains fine enough to distinguish the large majority of nearby designated parking locations, while avoiding unnecessarily coarse aggregation of locally distinct parking structures. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances and shows the selected 25 m resolution in relation to the empirical spacing of designated parking locations.

Figure 2: Distribution of nearest-neighbour distances between designated parking locations in Düsseldorf. The vertical line marks the 25 m spatial resolution used in the analysis.

A third consideration concerns interoperability. For dashboard-based reporting and possible future cross-city comparisons, the grid should remain compatible with a harmonized European reference-grid logic. In the present study, this is achieved by defining the 25 m grid as an ETRS89-LAEA-based subgrid aligned with the INSPIRE reference framework [19].

Taken together, these three considerations suggest that spatial resolution should be treated as part of the methodological design of the index. In the present study, 25 m was adopted as an empirically informed compromise. It lies within the range suggested by GPS-related uncertainty, remains below the lower tail of typical station spacing, and is compatible with a harmonized European grid logic. Compared with 20 m, it offers slightly greater robustness against positional scatter while avoiding unnecessary additional sparsity.

4 Design Requirements for BI-Compatible Indices

If a spatial order index is to support recurring dashboard-based monitoring rather than only one-off analysis, it must remain meaningful under aggregation. In multidimensional databases (OLAP) and statistical databases, analysis is largely based on summarization operations (for example roll-up and drill-down) across classification hierarchies and dimensions. Lenz and Shoshani [20] formalize this requirement as *summarizability*, that is, the conditions under which summarization operations produce the correct result and thus prevent erroneous conclusions from aggregated data.

4.1 Additivity as the Preferred Design Principle

A particularly robust design principle for BI-compatible indices is to prefer additive (extensive) measures wherever possible. Conceptually, this matches the classical definition of an extensive property, for example in thermodynamics, as an additive property: the value for a whole equals the sum of the values of its constituent parts. This additivity property is exactly what enables consistent roll-ups along arbitrary hierarchies (time, space, provider, vehicle class), because the aggregation operator, typically SUM, yields results that are independent of the path of aggregation.

In OLAP systems, this preference can be grounded in the established taxonomy of aggregate functions. Gray et al. [21] distinguish distributive aggregates (for example SUM, MIN, MAX, COUNT), algebraic aggregates (for example AVG, standard deviation) and holistic aggregates (for example median, rank), where distributive aggregates permit “aggregates to be aggregated” and holistic aggregates do not have a bounded-size representation that supports efficient and exact super-aggregation. This classification directly maps to practical BI requirements: indices derived from distributive, and with care algebraic, aggregates are generally summarizable and scalable, while holistic measures tend to be problematic for exact roll-ups.

4.2 Decomposability for Non-Additive Indices

Many measures of practical interest are inherently non-additive, including ratios, indices, and entropies. In such cases, good BI design does not mean avoiding them, but ensuring *decomposability*: the final index should be computable from additive base components that can be summarized correctly first, and only then transformed into the final measure.

Gray et al. [21] provide a clear theoretical template for this: algebraic aggregates can be computed via a fixed-size intermediate state, for example storing SUM and COUNT as components for AVG, which enables correct computation at higher aggregation levels.

In BI practice, this implies that a ratio or index should be represented by its numerator and denominator

components in the fact layer, and the final measure should be computed only after aggregation in the semantic layer. This approach aligns with the general summarizability motivation emphasized by Lenz and Shoshani [20]: without correct summarizability conditions, aggregation can yield incorrect results and, consequently, erroneous decisions.

4.3 From BI Requirements to an Entropy-Based Index

The BI requirements discussed above favor indices that are stable under slicing, filtering, and hierarchical aggregation, and that can therefore be computed from summarizable base measures. In practice, this means storing fully additive primitives at a well-defined grain and deriving higher-level indicators only after the reporting level of interest has been fixed (e.g., month, provider subset, or spatial region). In our setting, the most natural primitives are spatial counts: after discretizing the study area into a fixed set of grid cells, we store the number of observations per cell and time t . These counts are distributive and can be summed consistently across time roll-ups, provider segments, and other BI dimensions. Importantly, the collection of cell counts constitutes a complete, BI-friendly representation of the spatial distribution at the chosen grain.

Given such a frequency representation, Shannon entropy is a particularly suitable candidate because it is a theoretically grounded scalar functional of a discrete distribution rather than an ad hoc concentration score. Uncertainty can be interpreted as the inverse of structural order: highly concentrated, predictable distributions correspond to more ordered systems, whereas diffuse, unpredictable ones reflect a lack of structure.

A fundamental perspective arises from the information content of individual events. For an event with probability p , let $I(p) = -\log_2 p$ denote its information content. Requiring that independent events contribute additively, $I(pq) = I(p) + I(q)$, uniquely determines this logarithmic form. Shannon entropy is then defined as the expected information across the distribution:

$$H = \sum_i p_i I(p_i) = - \sum_i p_i \log_2 p_i.$$

For BI purposes, the key point is not that entropy itself is additive, but that it can be expressed as a deterministic function of additive, summarizable count-based primitives. Within a system with total count $C = \sum_i c_i > 0$, the event probabilities are determined by the observed cell counts via $p_i = c_i/C$. Cells with $p_i = 0$ remain part of the fixed support, and their contribution is defined by continuity because $p \log_2 p \rightarrow 0$ as $p \rightarrow 0$. Substituting the empirical probabilities into Shannon entropy yields the count-based representation

$$H = \log_2 C - \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i: c_i > 0} c_i \log_2 c_i.$$

To make this BI bridge explicit, we define the per-cell contributions

$$s_i = \begin{cases} c_i \log_2(c_i), & c_i > 0, \\ 0, & c_i = 0. \end{cases}$$

We refer to these quantities as the *Stirling terms*. Aggregating them over the full fixed support gives

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^N s_i,$$

and entropy can therefore be written compactly as

$$H = \log_2 C - \frac{S}{C}. \tag{1}$$

This decomposition exposes additive sufficient statistics that can be precomputed at the lowest grain and aggregated across dimensions. At query time, entropy is then obtained from the aggregated components by applying a single $\log_2 C$ and one division. In this way, Shannon’s logarithmic form directly supports an efficient compute-after-aggregate workflow in BI systems, avoids repeated per-cell logarithms, ensures reproducibility under common BI operations, and enables consistent comparisons across time and segments.

Building on this rationale, [section 5](#) formalizes the Spatial Order Index by defining the fixed spatial discretization and summarizable count representation, deriving the induced probability distribution, and introducing Shannon entropy together with its normalization into the final index used for the empirical study.

5 Method and Index Definition

Having established why the need for an order index leads to BI requirements and why Shannon entropy satisfies them in count-based form, this section formalizes the proposed Spatial Order Index. Building on the decomposition introduced in [equation \(1\)](#), it defines the reporting grain, the fixed spatial discretization, and the normalized index used in the empirical study.

5.1 Reporting Grain and Summarizable Base Measures

Let A denote the analysis area, for example a city boundary, a zone system, or buffers around hubs. For each evaluation time t , we observe a set of vehicle positions $\{(x_k, y_k)\}$, where (x, y) denote projected spatial coordinates derived from longitude and latitude. At the base level of observation, t therefore denotes a snapshot time. When temporal aggregation is introduced later, the same index denotes the resulting reporting window.

To obtain a stable, summarizable representation, A is partitioned into N non-overlapping spatial cells of equal area, for example a square grid or hexagonal tiling. The choice of cell size is discussed in detail in [section 3](#).

For each cell i and time t , let $c_{i,t}$ denote the number of observed vehicles located in cell i . We define the corresponding cell-wise Stirling term by

$$s_{i,t} = \begin{cases} c_{i,t} \log_2(c_{i,t}), & c_{i,t} > 0, \\ 0, & c_{i,t} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Aggregating across all cells yields

$$C_t = \sum_{i=1}^N c_{i,t}, \quad S_t = \sum_{i=1}^N s_{i,t}. \quad (3)$$

The cell-wise quantities $\{c_{i,t}\}_{i=1}^N$ and $\{s_{i,t}\}_{i=1}^N$, together with their totals C_t and S_t , are additive primitives: they can be summed across compatible hierarchies (time roll-ups, spatial roll-ups when based on unions of cells, provider grouping) without changing their meaning [21]. This property is the foundation for summarizability in OLAP-style reporting [20].

To make the count-based representation more intuitive, [figure 3](#) provides a purely schematic illustration. In both panels, the number of grid cells and the total number of observations are identical. What differs is only the spatial distribution across cells: a broader spread corresponds to higher entropy and lower spatial order, whereas concentration in fewer cells corresponds to lower entropy and higher spatial order.

(a) The same total number of observations is spread broadly across the grid.

(b) The same total number of observations is concentrated in a smaller subset of cells.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of the count-based principle behind the Spatial Order Index. In both examples, the number of grid cells and the total number of observations are identical. Only the spatial distribution differs: a broader spread corresponds to higher entropy and lower spatial order, whereas concentration in fewer cells corresponds to lower entropy and higher spatial order.

5.2 From Counts to the Spatial Order Index

For times t with $C_t > 0$, we define the empirical probability distribution over grid cells as

$$p_{i,t} = \frac{c_{i,t}}{C_t}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

with $\sum_{i=1}^N p_{i,t} = 1$.

Using the count-based decomposition from [equation \(1\)](#), entropy at time t can be written as

$$H_t = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_{i,t} \log_2(p_{i,t}) = \log_2 C_t - \frac{S_t}{C_t}, \quad (5)$$

where S_t is the aggregated sum of the cell-wise Stirling terms defined in [equation \(3\)](#). Because zero-count cells satisfy $s_{i,t} = 0$ by [equation \(2\)](#), all N grid cells remain part of the fixed support without requiring special handling in subsequent sums.

To obtain a bounded index with stable interpretation, entropy is normalized by its maximum for the given grid:

$$H_{\max} = \log_2(N), \quad H_t^{\text{norm}} = \frac{H_t}{H_{\max}} \in [0, 1].$$

Because the objective is to quantify order rather than disorder, we define the Spatial Order Index as

$$O_t = 1 - H_t^{\text{norm}} = 1 - \frac{H_t}{\log_2(N)} \in [0, 1]. \quad (6)$$

Interpretation:

- $O_t \rightarrow 1$: strong concentration into few cells (high spatial order / pronounced clustering).
- $O_t \rightarrow 0$: near-uniform spread over the grid (low spatial order / high dispersion).

5.3 BI-Compatible Computation Rule

For consistent roll-up / drill-down behavior, the following computation rule is applied:

1. **Summarize first:** aggregate the additive base measures $c_{i,t}$ and $s_{i,t}$ to the requested reporting level (time roll-up, spatial region selection, provider grouping, etc.), yielding the corresponding totals C_t and S_t .
2. **Compute second:** derive H_t and O_t from the aggregated components.

This design ensures that the index is reproducible, avoids incorrect aggregation of aggregates, and remains compatible with summarizability requirements in multidimensional reporting. It also makes the index operationally scalable because the stored primitives are distributive measures, whereas the final indicator is computed only after aggregation at the reporting level.

6 Empirical Study: Parking-Prohibition Zones

With the Spatial Order Index now defined, the remainder of the paper evaluates its empirical usefulness for monitoring geofenced parking regulation in Düsseldorf.

6.1 Study Area and Motivation

To evaluate the proposed Spatial Order Index, the analysis covers all parking-prohibition zones in Düsseldorf. This provides a broader and more robust empirical basis than a single area alone and reflects the practical setting in which geofenced parking regulation is actually implemented in the city.

Most of these zones correspond to district centres and other high-activity urban areas where micromobility parking is particularly visible and policy-relevant because pedestrian density, mixed land use, and competition for public space are high. A smaller number of zones serve more specific purposes, such as the area around the youth hostel or localized exclusion zones introduced in response to concrete parking problems, for example complaints about vehicles being parked in a fire access area. Taken together, the full set of zones captures both the main urban centres in which parking regulation is most consequential and smaller special-purpose areas shaped by local intervention needs.

As an illustrative example, Zone A (see [figure 4](#)) covers the core of Düsseldorf's inner city, including Altstadt, Carlstadt, Stadtmitte, and adjacent fringe areas that function as part of the same central urban system. As one of the city's most prominent high-pressure areas for micromobility parking, it provides a useful reference case for understanding the spatial logic of the wider set of parking-prohibition zones. For this reason, it is used as the example area in [section 6.5.1](#).

Figure 4: Parking-prohibition Zone A as an illustrative example of a central parking-prohibition zone in Düsseldorf. Basemap: Stadtplanwerk Ruhrgebiet 2.0 © Regionalverband Ruhr und Kooperationspartner (dl-de/by-2-0) [22].

6.2 Data Basis and Observation Period

We use vehicle position observations from the MDS /vehicles endpoint as described in section 2. The main observation period spans 1 January 2023 to 31 March 2026.

Across this period, the dataset comprises 270,233,043 observations covering 1186 days and 39 complete months. The dataset includes data from four providers. Data completeness was assessed at the hourly level; overall snapshot coverage was 98.6%, and no day was completely missing from the dataset.

To support BI-compatible aggregation and ensure comparability over time, the analysis is based on a fixed spatial discretization and a fixed temporal reporting grain. The final entropy-based indicators are computed only after aggregation at the reporting level.

6.3 Experimental Design

6.3.1 Spatial Discretization

Using the notation introduced in section 5, the full set of parking-prohibition zones is discretized into a fixed grid of N equal-area cells. For each reporting period t , cell-wise counts $c_{i,t}$ and Stirling terms $s_{i,t}$ are aggregated across all cells to obtain C_t and S_t . Entropy and the Spatial Order Index are then computed from these aggregated quantities according to equation (5) and equation (6).

We use a square grid with a spatial resolution of 25 m across the analysis area. Using the adopted support definition, this discretization yields $N = 20,738$ grid cells across the full set of parking-prohibition zones. This choice is consistent with the resolution analysis in section 3, balancing robustness, local separability, and interoperability. The resulting grid structure is visible in the spatial visualizations discussed later.

6.3.2 Temporal Aggregation

A key advantage of the proposed index is that it can be computed directly at any chosen reporting grain. Rather than averaging entropy values across lower-level time slices, the underlying count-based primitives are first aggregated to the reporting level of interest, and the Spatial Order Index is then derived from the resulting distribution. This follows the compute-after-aggregate principle introduced in [section 5.3](#).

In the present empirical study, the core indicator is computed at monthly granularity. Hourly vehicle observations are aggregated to monthly cell counts, from which entropy and the Spatial Order Index are calculated directly. This design avoids treating entropy itself as an object of temporal averaging and preserves consistency with BI-style roll-up logic.

6.3.3 Outcome Variables

The primary outcome is the Spatial Order Index O_t for the full set of parking-prohibition zones. Because the robustness of entropy estimates may still be affected by data completeness and unusually sparse observations, the corresponding observation volume C_t is monitored as a diagnostic quantity.

We therefore report at minimum:

- O_t : Spatial Order Index across all parking-prohibition zones.
- C_t : total number of observations across all parking-prohibition zones per reporting window (exposure / volume).

6.4 Results

6.4.1 Evolution of Spatial Order Over Time

[Figure 5](#) presents the evolution of the Spatial Order Index across the full set of parking-prohibition zones over the study period. As designated parking locations and related operational measures matured, the observed distribution became less diffuse and more concentrated into recurring hotspot structures, reflected by increasing order and decreasing normalized entropy.

Across the study period, the Spatial Order Index aggregated over all parking-prohibition zones shows a clear upward trend, rising from 0.225 in January 2023 to 0.367 in early 2026. This corresponds to an absolute increase of about 0.14, or about 63% relative to the initial level. The trend is driven by a sustained decline in entropy, while the normalization term remains constant. In practical terms, this indicates that parked vehicles became progressively more concentrated into a smaller subset of grid cells across the regulated areas of the city, that is, more spatially ordered and more strongly organized around recurring hotspot structures rather than diffusely distributed across the available state space.

Values are not expected to approach the extremes of 0 or 1 in a realistic urban setting, since the observed distribution is neither perfectly uniform nor concentrated in a single cell. The relevant result is therefore not the absolute proximity to the boundaries, but the clear and persistent increase over time. Month-to-month fluctuations remain visible, suggesting seasonal and operational variability, but they are clearly superimposed on a long-term upward trend in spatial order.

6.4.2 Association with the Rollout of Designated Parking Locations

To contextualize changes in spatial order with the development of operational infrastructure, we analyze the association between the Spatial Order Index and the rollout of designated parking locations. The

Figure 5: Spatial Order Index O_t across all parking-prohibition zones (monthly aggregates) over the three-year observation period, exhibiting a sustained increase.

underlying question is whether increases in spatial order across the regulated parking-prohibition zones coincide with the growth and maturation of the designated-parking network.

Figure 6 relates the monthly Spatial Order Index O_t , computed over the full set of parking-prohibition zones, to the number of designated parking locations. The scatter plot suggests a strong positive association: higher counts of designated parking locations are consistently associated with higher values of the index. This pattern is also reflected in the Pearson correlation coefficient [23] shown in the figure ($r = 0.969$), indicating a very strong linear relationship between network rollout and increasing spatial order.

Figure 6: Monthly Spatial Order Index O_t versus the number of designated parking locations. The plot indicates a strong positive association between network rollout and increasing spatial order, measured here by the Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.969$).

Substantively, this result is consistent with the interpretation that the expansion of the designated-parking network contributed to a more structured and less diffuse parking pattern across the regulated areas of

the city. As the number of designated parking locations increased, vehicle observations became more concentrated in a smaller subset of recurring hotspots, which is exactly the type of change captured by the Spatial Order Index. At the same time, the figure should be interpreted as evidence of association rather than strict causality. Network rollout was part of a broader regulatory and operational context that may also have included learning effects, enforcement, and changes in user behavior. Nevertheless, the strength and consistency of the observed association strongly support the view that the growing network of designated parking locations was closely linked to the measured increase in spatial order.

6.5 Local Rollout Monitoring in the University Area

Figure 7 shows the monthly Spatial Order Index O_t for the University Area. In contrast to the more gradual city-wide development, the local series suggests a more step-like pattern, with a marked increase from roughly 0.30 to about 0.55. This makes the area a useful example for examining whether the indicator is able to capture rollout-related changes not only at the aggregate city level, but also within a more localized intervention setting.

Figure 7: Monthly Spatial Order Index O_t for the University Area. The series shows an almost step-like increase from roughly 0.30 to about 0.55, illustrating the suitability of the indicator for monitoring rollout-related changes in a newly developed area.

The timing of the increase is consistent with the local rollout pattern summarized in table 1. In particular, the main jump in the indicator coincides with the major deployment wave of 2023-09-22, when 12 designated parking locations were introduced. By contrast, the earlier activation on 2023-02-03 involved only three locations, while the later activation on 2023-11-27 added only one further location. The September intervention therefore appears to have been the dominant rollout event within the area.

Table 1: Deployment of designated parking locations in the University Area by activation date.

Activation Date	Number of Stations
2023-02-03	3
2023-09-22	12
2023-11-27	1

At the same time, the limited increase at the beginning of the local rollout is also plausible. If the first interventions were placed primarily in locations that were already local parking hotspots, then they may initially have reorganized parking within an already active subset of cells rather than substantially narrowing the overall spatial support. In such a situation, local hotspots are formalized or slightly shifted, but the distribution remains concentrated in broadly the same part of the area. The resulting effect on O_t can therefore remain modest even though designated parking locations are already present.

The later step-like increase is substantively different. It suggests not merely a redistribution within an existing hotspot area, but a clearer transition from a comparatively diffuse parking pattern toward a more selective and structured use of a smaller subset of grid cells. In this sense, the local series supports the interpretation that the indicator is sensitive not only to gradual long-term consolidation, but also to more discrete changes associated with major rollout phases in newly developed subareas.

The University Area therefore complements the aggregate city-wide results. It suggests that the Spatial Order Index can serve not only as a reporting measure for the full set of parking-prohibition zones, but also as a practical monitoring instrument for the expansion of regulated parking structures in specific subareas. As in the city-wide analysis, this pattern should be interpreted as evidence of association rather than strict causality, since the rollout was embedded in a broader operational context.

6.5.1 Hotspot Structure and Spatial Explainability

To make the entropy-based Spatial Order Index more interpretable, it is useful to complement the scalar time series with spatial visualizations that show where concentration actually occurs. This is particularly relevant for Zone A, the largest parking-prohibition zone in Düsseldorf and the city’s main high-pressure area for micromobility parking management. As the core of the inner city, with high pedestrian volumes, dense mixed land use, strong public transport interchanges, and intense competition for curb space, Zone A is where parking-management measures are expected to affect vehicle distribution most visibly. It therefore provides a particularly relevant test bed for examining whether changes in the index correspond to meaningful changes in the underlying spatial pattern.

Figure 8 and figure 9 provide a qualitative hotspot comparison for an early and a late reference month. The maps are based on the same 25 m grid discretization that underlies the index calculation. Using the cell counts $c_{i,t}$ and totals C_t introduced in section 5, the query computes the cell-wise share $p_{i,t}$ for each timestamp. To obtain a stable monthly visualization, these shares are then averaged over all query times in the selected month:

$$\bar{p}_i = \frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{t \in T} p_{i,t},$$

where T is the set of query times in the month. The resulting heatmaps show the average vehicle share per grid cell over the selected month. For each query time, cell counts are normalized by the total number of vehicles observed in Zone A, and the resulting shares are then averaged across all query times in the month.

Figure 8: Average vehicle share per 25 m grid cell in Zone A for January 2023.

Figure 9: Average vehicle share per 25 m grid cell in Zone A for March 2026. The colour scale is kept consistent with figure 8.

The comparison suggests a clear structural shift. In the early period, vehicle shares are distributed across a broader set of cells, with a relatively diffuse low-intensity background and several local concentration points. In the later period, the pattern becomes more selective: a smaller number of cells accounts for a larger share of observed vehicles, while large parts of the zone contribute less to the monthly average. In other words, the spatial support becomes narrower and the recurring hotspots become more pronounced relative to the surrounding area.

It should also be noted that some hotspot formation is already visible in the early period, particularly in the central part of the map around the Altstadt area. This is plausible given that several designated parking locations already existed in Zone A in 2023. The later pattern can therefore be interpreted less as the first emergence of spatial order than as a further consolidation and sharpening of an already developing hotspot structure.

This visual change is consistent with the increase in the Spatial Order Index reported above. The rise in O_t is therefore not merely a formal consequence of the entropy calculation, but corresponds to a recognizable reorganization of parking behaviour in space. The heatmaps thus provide an important qualitative validation of the index by linking the scalar trend to concrete and interpretable hotspot structures.

6.6 Interim Conclusion

Taken together, the empirical study completes the argumentative sequence developed in the paper: starting from the need for an order index, deriving BI requirements, motivating an entropy-based solution via count-based decomposition, and then evaluating the resulting Spatial Order Index on operational data from Düsseldorf. Across the full set of parking-prohibition zones, the analysis demonstrates that the index can be operationalized in a BI-compatible way (summarizable primitives, deterministic derivation) and interpreted alongside infrastructure rollout (designated parking locations) and exposure measures. By moving from a single-zone perspective to the full set of regulated areas, the study also provides a broader and statistically more robust basis for assessing whether geofenced parking regulation is associated with measurable changes in spatial order at the city level. The next step is to extend the analysis from descriptive trends to intervention-aware comparisons, for example pre/post rollout phases, control zones, or difference-in-differences designs, depending on the availability of policy milestone dates and comparable reference areas.

Optional Extensions. To strengthen the empirical analysis beyond the three core plots (order, volume, and station count), several additional diagnostics may be useful: a weekday-versus-weekend split, seasonal decomposition, lag analysis after station rollout, boundary-effect checks, the effective number of occupied cells,

$$k_{\text{eff},t} = 2^{H_t},$$

which indicates how many equally used cells would produce the observed entropy, and state-conditioned versions of the index. In particular, computing the Spatial Order Index separately for harmonized vehicle-state classes could help distinguish whether observed changes in spatial order are driven mainly by parked vehicles or by other operational subpopulations. Such analyses would, however, require careful harmonization of provider-specific state definitions.

7 Outlook and Possible Future Improvements

While the proposed index is intentionally defined in a generic and BI-compatible way, several extensions could be explored in future work. In the present definition, the maximum-entropy reference is $\log_2(N)$, where N is the number of grid cells in the analysis area. This provides a transparent and reproducible normalization, but it also implies that very high values of O_t correspond to concentration into a very small subset of the available state space.

In practice, however, an operational target may be less extreme. Future work could therefore consider target-aware normalizations, for example by replacing $\log_2(N)$ with a reference based on an effective hotspot capacity or on designated hub locations. This could make the index more directly interpretable in policy and management contexts while preserving the current BI-compatible decomposition into additive base measures.

A further topic for future work is the harmonization of the spatial discretization for cross-city comparison. While the present study adopts a 25 m square grid for the Düsseldorf case, comparative applications may require a common square-grid design to ensure that differences in the index reflect urban structure rather than differences in spatial tessellation.

Although the empirical study in this paper is based on MDS /vehicles data and additional manually curated operational geodata, the index can in principle also be computed from GBFS-based or comparable status feeds, provided that sufficiently granular spatial snapshots are available. Compared with MDS-based applications, however, GBFS-based applications may offer a less detailed operational state and event representation. If the index is used for intervention-oriented analyses, additional contextual geodata may be required, depending on the local setup.

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